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**RADİASIYA VƏ KİMYƏVİ TƏHLÜKƏSİZLİK
PROBLEMLƏRİ**

Beynəlxalq elmi-praktik Konfrans

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THERMOLUMINESCENCE DATING ON CERAMICS

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Thermoluminescence (TL) dating is a technique that is based on the analysis of light release when heating crystalline material. TL-dating is used in mineralogy and geology, but is also increasingly being applied for dating of anthropological, archaeological samples. This method is mainly used for pottery analysis.

TL originates from the temperature induced release of energy, stored in the lattice structure of the crystal following long-term internal and external exposure to nuclear radiation from natural sources. TL accumulates in the material with time depending on the radiation (and light) exposure. The amount of accumulated TL is proportional to the age of the sample and inverse proportional to the nuclear radiation exposure of the sample. Amount of energy E deposited by radiation exposure into sample of mass m within one year. It depends on the content of radioactive nuclei in the sample material and on the exposure to external radioactivity.

The Plateau Test is significant for measurements. Fig. 1 illustrates the ratio of glow curve sample from Chuxur -Gabala archaeological site. The curve represents the ratio of the two glow-curves i.e. $I_{0\text{Gy}}$ natural TL and $I_{4.8\text{Gy}}$ -irradiated at 4.8 Gy. The plateau level of 0,7 indicates that the dose equivalent to the natural TL is $0,7/(1-0,7)$, i.e. 2.33 times the artificial dose used (4.8 Gy in this case). Hence the equivalent dose is equal to $2.33 \times 4.8 = 11.2$ Gy.

Figure 1 Plateau test

